

MedVetKlebs: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from ecology to source attribution and transmission control

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D-4.3. Communication Strategy Plan

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1. Current situation and background

Before creating the formal communication plan, communication actions about the project had already taken place:

- Announcement of the project funding by One Health EJP through website and EJP activities management: <https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-medvetklebs/>
- The project website was created on Dec 20th, 2017: <https://research.pasteur.fr/en/project/medvetklebs-klebsiella-pneumoniae-ecology-source-attribution-transmission-control/>
- Kick-off meeting took place on January 11-12th, 2018
- Tweets mentioned #MedVetKlebs (<https://twitter.com/hashtag/medvetklebs>) in Twitter since January 2018 on the occasion of meetings (Year 1 MedVetKlebs meeting, OneHealth EJP scientific meeting ANSES Jan 28th, 2018) or publications (ZKIR qPCR preprint in bioRxiv, Aug 19th, 2019).
- MedVetKlebs was advertised/discussed within *Klebsiella* microbiology/surveillance research projects (SpARK, KlebNET, Nor-Kleb-Net).
- Communication towards industry (BioMérieux, Bruker) about MALDI-TOF MS method to identify *Klebsiella*.

2. Communication objectives

Internal communication is intended to facilitate diffusion of information among the partners (e.g., about publication or oral presentations). This is considered as being part of the project management and takes place as planned (three plenary meetings over the two years - Jan 11th, 2018; Jan 10th, 2019; April 16th, 2020); one meeting at OneHealth EJP ASM in Dublin; plus regular e-mails and *ad-hoc* TCs). Here we define external communication objectives.

Our communication objectives are:

- To develop awareness about the project among microbiologists interested in *Klebsiella*;
- To develop awareness about the project in the **One Health** community;
- To reach out to **surveillance networks** and **institutions** (e.g., GLASS, ECDC EuScape, EFSA) about the project and its main achievements in order for them to

consider integration of *Klebsiella* in surveillance activities and to promote the uptake of our novel methods and data;

- To encourage and facilitate the **build-up of an international and cross-sector community** interested in bridging the gap between surveillance and research on *Klebsiella*; especially in the context of antimicrobial resistance surveillance and control;
- To increase general public awareness of the importance of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and its contribution to antimicrobial resistance and the project benefits in this area.

3. Target audience

The target audience of our communication objectives is defined for each objective (in the objectives themselves). It is mainly research/surveillance professional communities and networks, either with a specific interest in *Klebsiella* and One Health approaches, or with activities where knowing about MedVetKlebs would be highly relevant.

- **Scientific community:** Researchers working in the field or in similar research lines.
- **Research/surveillance professional communities and institutions.** Public, private and political institutions and other authorities. The close contact with these institutions is key to the successful implementation of the research developed in the project.
- **Industrial companies.** Companies from the microbiology sector (e.g. Bruker, BioMérieux) interested in incorporating the results (e.g. MALDI-TOF ID of the member from *K. pneumoniae* and *K. oxytoca* complex) of our research in their platforms/commercial products.
- **Society:** General public or professional stakeholders, interested in *K. pneumoniae* with respect to its contribution to the burden of antibiotic resistance; and what research is being conducted in this respect within the MedVetKlebs consortium.

Apart from the target audiences aforementioned, we also have the internal communication among partners of the consortium, which is ensured through meetings, regular e-mails and *ad-hoc* TCs, as previously mentioned.

3.1. Key message per target audience

- **For *Klebsiella* researchers:** knowledge about MedVetKlebs objectives, and how they can benefit from MedVetKlebs achievements, or contribute to the project themselves.
- **For the One Health community:** knowledge about the MedVetKlebs project as an example of a One Health approach for a ubiquitous bacterial pathogen. Raise interest in discussing challenges, strategies and achievements from the example of *Klebsiella*.
- **For the surveillance networks and agencies/authorities:** awareness of the MedVetKlebs objectives, expertise and developed harmonized protocols/tools.
- **For the international community involved in antimicrobial resistance networking for research and surveillance:** to invite participation to join forces around *Klebsiella* research and surveillance.

4. MedVetKlebs logo and templates

4.1. Logo

A logo (**Figure 1**) with the purpose of the public clearly identify and associate our research to the MedVetKlebs project was created by Sylvain Brisse and Sophie Guillot at the beginning of the project (December 2017).

Figure 1. MedVetKlebs logo

The logo represents the evolution of *Klebsiella* across different hosts, using an analogy to the ‘chain of evolution’ classical representation. This logo reflects one of the main ambitions

of the MedVetKlebs project - bring *Klebsiella* ecology from a neglected status to solid baseline knowledge by using an integrated population biology and epidemiological approach. In order to facilitate the identification and recognition of MedVetKlebs project, the logo is used by all partners in the different communication media used (website, social networks, photos, oral presentations, reports, press release, ...)

4.2. Official Templates

One Health EJP templates for poster and oral communications have been adopted in our project. These templates have been designed to unify the external communications of the partners and to easily recognize the link of the projects to the One Health EJP programme.

4.3. Acknowledgments section

In all communications carried out, both internally and externally, the logo of One Health EJP must be shown. This facilitates the association of our project to the One Health EJP programme. Furthermore, in the case of scientific publications an acknowledgment section is included with the following phrase: “This work was supported financially by the MedVetKlebs project, a component of European Joint Programme One Health EJP, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.”

5. Communication strategy

The detailed communication planning is shown in **Table 1**. The information carried in this table will be updated during the course of MedVetKlebs project, until the final version of this communication plan.

5.1. Scientific communications

- **Scientific Publications** in *open access* journals
- **Congresses:** posters and oral presentations. MedVetKlebs partners will take part in relevant congresses to the scientific domain of the project (e.g. One Health EJP ASM; ECCMID; IMMEM; other One Health meetings...)
- **Organization of seminars/workshops:** none so far

5.2. Online communication and social networks

- **Websites** - <https://research.pasteur.fr/en/project/medvetklebs-klebsiella-pneumoniae-ecology-source-attribution-transmission-control/> and <https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-medvetklebs/>. The first one was created in order to present an overview of the topic of project with the description of the main goals. In the second one, aside from the information about the project, the website is also used as a platform for dissemination of information content generated through the project (publications, information about the partners, project events and project deliverables) being updated regularly.
- **Social networks** - The main goals of using social networks in MedVetKlebs project are focus on: bring research carried out to the general public; serve as a channel for mass distribution of scientific and social updates of the project; to advertise events (e.g. congresses) attended by partners of MedVetKlebs project; to establish and maintain closer relationships with the target audiences; and also, if necessary, to carry out recruitment processes for the project. In our case, Twitter (<https://twitter.com/> using the hashtag [#MedVetKlebs](#) and [#OneHealth](#)) (**Figure 2**) has been recognized as the most useful social network to target MedVetKlebs audience. We link to @OneHealthEJP as appropriate.

Figure 2. #MedVetKlebs tweet (on Twitter)

5.3. Public relations

- E-mails, phone calls to target persons
- Invitations at our final meeting & combining with KlebNET partners
- Press release upon important publication
- Newsletters – One Health Internal Newsletter Volume 3- February 2019
(<https://mailchi.mp/427607c3583d/ohejp-february-newsletter-review-313813>)

5.4. Specific Dissemination activities

In addition to the above communications, which are also dissemination activities given their target audiences, we will take the following actions to disseminate our results:

a) Open data access

Please refer to our Data management plan for details.

b) Open protocols on protocols.io (<https://www.protocols.io>)

To increase the impact of our research results regarding methods development and harmonization, we have set-up a *Klebsiella* Research and Surveillance group on protocols.io, and started populating it with protocols:

- ZKIR qPCR protocol published ahead of publication:
dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.7n6hmhe
- SCAI protocol and isolation of *Klebsiella* strains from human or animal fecal material
- dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.662hhge
- Others in process: isolation of *Klebsiella* strains from other sources; Phylogroup-specific qPCR, ...

6. Budget

The communication budget will be taken from the MedVetKlebs management budget or using missions/travel/publication budgets of partners.

7. Evaluation/Reporting

In order to evaluate the success of our communication activities and, if necessary, to reinforce the strategies, we will use some metrics, such as:

- Quotes of our publications
- Number of publications in the media (press release)
- Uptake of protocols by colleagues/networks
- Twitter - number of mentions, comments and interactions
- Number of visitors in the webpage

Table 1. Communication planning

ACTIVITIES	TARGET DATE	AUDIENCE	LEAD CONTRIBUTORS	STATUS	NOTES
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS	December 2018	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities Industrial Companies	SB, CR, VP	Final	https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000
	February 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities	SB, CR, VP	Final	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003 DOI 10.1099/ijsem.0.003624
	June 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities		Final	https://doi.org/10.1097/INF.0000000000002258
	October 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities	SB, CR, VP	Final	https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.02360
CONGRESSES	October 2018	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities Industrial Companies	SB, CR, VP	Final	Poster Presentation at Congrès National de la Société Française de Microbiologie
	May 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities Industrial Companies	IP, INRA, ANSES, SSI, ISZAM	Final	1 oral and 6 poster presentations at One Health EJP ASM
	September 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities	IP, ANSES	Final	1 oral presentation at 12 th International Meeting on Microbial Epidemiological Markers (IMMEM XII)

EXTERNAL MEETINGS	April 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities	All partners invited	Final	1 st KlebNET (https://research.pasteur.fr/en/project/klebnet-a-one-health-network-bridging-science-and-surveillance-on-antimicrobial-resistant-klebsiella/) meeting at 29 th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases (ECCMID)
NEWSLETTERS	February 2018	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities Industrial Companies General Society	SB, CR	In progress	https://mailchi.mp/427607c3583d/ohejp-february-newsletter-review-313813
SOCIAL NETWORKS	NA	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities Industrial Companies General Society	SB	In progress	Twitter (#MedVetKlebs)
OPEN ACCESS PROTOCOLS	August 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities	IP, INRA	Final	dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.7n6hmhe
	September 2019	Scientific community Surveillance networks/authorities	SB, CR, VP	Final	dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.662hhge

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